

MATHEMATICS FROM SCIENCE APPROPRIATION DIFFICULT HAS BEEN VISUAL TEACHING OF ISSUES METHODOLOGY (BRACKETS TO OPEN RULES. COEFFICIENTS EXAMPLE)

Zakirova Nargiza Sadriddin’s daughter

Muradova Kamala Akramjanovna

Teacher of the Department of Applied Mathematics and
Digital Technologies of Namangan State University

zokirovan99@gmail.com

Annotation: In this article Mathematics from science student and future of teachers appropriations difficult has been of issues lighting and this issues of what consists of that determine, and appropriation difficult has been of issues in teaching computer technologies and computer from the games useful methods about data and brackets topic lighting about data showing passed.

Key words: Parentheses, parentheses to open rules and coefficients about word walking passed.

As we all know, the science of mathematics itself is considered difficult to study and learn in comparison to other sciences. However, a more in-depth study of some topics in mathematics can increase interest in mathematics.

In mathematics, one of the topics that are difficult to master and need to be studied is parentheses and it is appropriate to study the topic of operations within them.

It can be said that the rules of opening parentheses are important as a foundation in almost all classes.

To multiply to add relatively distribution of the law positive numbers for application with you don't know This the law joining to the number garden it's not and they are between Minus number 1gan cases too is the first place.

Most of the time calculations perform in the process *brackets to open* or common multiplier *from parentheses out to issue* right will come. In this the following to the rules compliance request to do will be done.

Rule 1. If bracket in front $\langle + \rangle$ hint standing if she is without brackets in opening bracket inside of contributors hints without changing bracket and $\langle + \rangle$ hint leave to send can:

$$a+(bc)=a+bc$$

1- example. $+(-10 + 8 - 12) = -10 + 8 - 12 = -14.$

Rule 2. If in parentheses the first without a plus sign written if in front $\langle + \rangle$ hint there is that assumption will be:

2- example. $-2.8 + (2.8 - 7.63) = -2.8 + 2.8 - 7.63 = -7.63$.

Rule 3. If the bracket in front $\langle - \rangle$ sign standing if she is without bracket inside adders look at the sign to shishiga replacing bracket to open need:

$$a-(b+c)=abc \quad a-(-b+c)=a+bc$$

3- example. $-(-7 + 8 - 14) = 7 - 8 + 14 = 13$.

Rule 4. If the total to brackets taking bracket forward "+" hint if put she is without to parenthesis received of contributors hints unchanged is left.

4- example. $-13 + 8 - 2 = +(-13 + 8 - 2) = +(-7) = -7$.

Rule 5. If the total to brackets taking bracket forward $\langle - \rangle$ hint if put she is without to parenthesis received of contributors hints opposite changes.

5- example. $11 - 18 + 16 - 23 = -(-11 + 18 - 16 + 23) = -(-14) = 14$.

Now, if we come to the concept of coefficients, I think it is known to everyone that coefficients serve as the main concepts of mathematics. Therefore, a reader who understands the subject of coefficients well, in my opinion, can fully implement the information.

If expression number and one how many from the multiplication of letters if it consists of 1, it is in front of the letter multiplier **coefficient** is called

$5 \cdot a \cdot \left(-\frac{4}{15}\right) \cdot b \cdot 7$ if we simplify the given expression.

Ye ch is h. By *simplifying an expression* shown practice s done him given than possible as long as more compact shorter or simpler in appearance writing get understood.

Expression more compact writing in getting of multiplication to us known 1gan properties help will give, ie all numerous multipliers letters forward our writing possible As a result to the following have we will:

$$5 \cdot a \cdot \left(-\frac{4}{15}\right) \cdot b \cdot 7 = \left(5 \cdot \left(-\frac{4}{15}\right) \cdot 7\right) \cdot (a \cdot b) = -\frac{28}{3} \cdot a \cdot b$$

The result given to expression relatively simple to look have it was

It would be appropriate to dwell separately on a few more ways of teaching the given issue

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